

Dela kumene kuli nyumba	Nambala ya Kafukufuku	Nambala ya chizindikiro cha nyumba

CHIKALATA CHA CHILOREZO

MUTU WA KAFUKUFUKU

4a. The epidemiology of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* at a household level in Malawi

Chilorezo chofotokozedwa bwino cha otenga nawo mbali azaka 8-18

Tikupanga kafukufuku wokhudzana ndi kufala kwa tizirombo ta **bacteria** m'nyumba. Kafukufukuyu ndi mbali imodzi yophunzira anthu, ziweto komanso chilengedwe. Mukapanga chisankho choti mukufuna kukhala nawo mukafukufuku, mupemphedwa kuti mutenge nawo mbali mu mchezo ndi wopangitsa kafukufukuyu komanso kupereka chimbudzi chanu kuti chikayesedwe.

Pali zinthu zina zokhudzana ndi kafukufukuyu zimene mukuyenera kuzidziwa. Gulu la kafukufukuyu lidzakuyenderani kawili mu sabata yoyambilira. Kutolera zoyesa kudzabwezedwa pambuyo pa mwenzi umodzi komanso pambuyo pa miyezi isanu ndi umodzi kuchokera pa tsiku loyambilira kukumana ndi gulu la kafukufuku. Tikuyembekeza kufunsa mafunso komanso kutenga zoyesa kuchokera kwa anthu komanso nyama m'nyumba, kuphatikizapo zachilengedwe zozungulira nyumba.

Si aliyense wotenga nawo mbali mukafukufukuyu amene angapindure. Phindu likutanthauza kuti chinthu chabwino chikuchitikirani. Tikuganizira kuti phindu limeneli likhoza kukhala lonena kuti ngati munthu wina aliyense kapena nyama m'nyumba zikunyamula tizirombo toopsya ta **bacteria** tidzapeza zimenezi pa nthawi imene kafukufukuyu akuchitika. Mwanjira imeneyi, kuopsya kukutanthauza kuti tizirombo ta **bacteria** timene tingathe kukupangitsani inu kuti mudwale. Kafukufukuyu akatha, tidzapereka lipoti pa zotsatira ndikupereka uphungu woyenelera kwa inu, pofuna kukutetezani kuti musadwale.

Tikathana ndi kafukufukuyu tidzalemba lipoti lokhudzana ndi zimene zinaphunziridwa. Lipotili silidzakhala ndi dzina lanu kapena kufotokoza kuti munali nawo mukafukufuku.

Simukuyenera kukhala nawo mukafukufukuyu ngati simukufuna kutero. Mukapanga chisankho chosiya titayambapo kale, zimenzu ndizabwinonso. Makolo anu kapena opereka chisamaliro akudziwa zokhudzana ndi kafukufukunso.

TENTACLE

Version 2.0

29th January 2019

Mukapanga chiganizo choti mukufuna kukhala nawo mukafukufukuyu, chonde sayinirani dzina lanu kapena ikani chidindo cha chala mu bokosi kumanja kwanu.

Ine, _____, ndikufuna kukhala nawo mukafukufukuyu.

(Sayinirani dzina lanu apa /chidindo cha chala) (Deti)

Chitsimikizo cha mboni yopanda mbali:

Ine, _____, ndikutsimikizira kuti _____
wavomereza kutenga nawo mbali mukafukufuku ali m'mwambamu

Sayini ya wogwira ntchito amene akutenga chilorezo: _____
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